

NICKEL ALUMINATE SPINEL-DERIVED CATALYSTS FOR THE AQUEOUS PHASE REFORMING OF GLYCEROL: EFFECT OF REDUCTION TEMPERATURE

A. Morales-Marín¹, J.L. Ayastuy^{1,*}, U. Iriarte-Velasco², M.A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz¹

Chemical Technologies for the Environmental Sustainability Group,

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology

University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU,

Sarriena S/N, 48940 Leioa, Spain

²Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Pharmacy

University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU,

Paseo de la Universidad, 7, 01006 Vitoria, Spain

**Corresponding author: joseluis.ayastuy@ehu.eus*

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1 **Abstract**

2 Bulk nickel aluminate (NiAl_2O_4) was synthesised by co-precipitation at a Ni/Al mole ratio of 1:2
3 (stoichiometric ratio). The prepared sample was reduced at different temperatures, in the 300 to 850
4 °C range, and obtained assays were analysed by a wide range of analytical techniques (XFR, XRD,
5 H_2 -chemisorption, H_2 -TPR, DRS UV-vis NIR, FTIR, ^{27}Al MAS NMR, NH_3 -TPD, CO_2 -TPD, TPO)
6 and tested for the APR of glycerol. The spinel precursor allowed the formation of small and stable Ni
7 particles (< 14 nm) upon reduction with good performance in the APR of glycerol (NiAl-850 93%
8 conversion, 57% conversion to gas, at 250 °C/45 bar and WHSV 24.5 h^{-1}). Hydrogen was the main
9 gaseous product and the activation temperature did not substantially alter selectivity to gaseous
10 products; however, selectivity to intermediate oxygenated liquid compounds was substantially
11 modified. Overall, glycerol dehydrogenation route was dominant at high reduction temperature. The
12 good stability of the spinel led to stable H_2 yield in the long-term runs (50 hours) and proved potential
13 to be used in the APR of glycerol.

14

15 1. Introduction

16 Glycerol (1,2,3-propanetriol) is a major by-product during the production of biodiesel by
17 transesterification of vegetable oils [1], animal fats [2] and waste oils [3]. Glycerol is generated at
18 approximately 10 wt.% of the total biodiesel produced. Thus, the huge increase in the worldwide
19 production of biodiesel [4] leads to a large amount of glycerol surplus, which must be recycled into
20 higher value-added chemicals for the economic viability of biodiesel industries. The high
21 functionalization of the glycerol molecule makes it prone to many different processes such as
22 oxidation, hydrogenolysis and dehydration [5].

23 Glycerol can be also used as hydrogen source, as alternative to the traditionally used catalytic steam
24 reforming of methane [6]. The catalytic aqueous phase reforming (APR) of biomass-derived
25 oxygenated hydrocarbons was introduced by first in 2002 by the group of Dumesic [7]. The process
26 can be carried out at relatively low temperatures (200-280 °C) and moderate pressures (15-70 bar) as
27 compared to gas-phase reforming and the selection of proper operation conditions, feedstreams and
28 catalysts can be used to drive the APR to either hydrogen or alkanes production [8]. Thus, undesirable
29 decomposition reactions, such as coke deposition, can be minimized whereas H₂ production can be
30 increased by the Water-Gas Shift reaction (WGS) [6]. APR is also energy-efficient since water and
31 glycerol are not vaporized. Moreover, the concentration of glycerol among the byproducts of
32 biodiesel is optimal to the APR, therefore no pre-treatment is required in order to adjust
33 water/glycerol ratio.

34 The ideal APR of glycerol yields seven moles of hydrogen and three moles of CO₂ per mole of
35 glycerol (Eqs. 1-3):

39 A catalyst with high H₂ selectivity must promote C-C and C-H bond cleavage and WGS reaction, and
40 should minimize the C-O cleavage (i.e. CO and CO₂ hydrogenation) [9]. Platinum, ruthenium and in
41 general, metals from Group VIII exhibit high APR activity [10-12]. Benchmark supported platinum
42 catalysts are recognized as the most active and selective catalysts due to their moderate activity in C-
43 C and C-H bond cleavage [6] and low methanation and Fisher-Tropsch activity [8]. In the recent
44 years, nickel based catalysts have attracted considerable attention for the APR process as due to
45 economic criteria as well as its good intrinsic activity in C-C scission, especially high by small
46 particles [11,13-16]. Nickel supported on conventional γ -alumina has been extensively investigated
47 because of adequate textural properties. However, under APR hydrothermal conditions, γ -Al₂O₃ can

48 be hydrated and transformed into boehmite (γ -AlOOH), with significant alteration of its surface area
49 and acidity. This may provoke activity decay [17] due to dissolution of the support and sinterisation
50 of metal particles [18].

51 The nature of oxide surfaces that support the metal phase are of critical importance [19,20]. Nickel
52 aluminate (NiAl_2O_4) spinels are known to present a partially inverted structure with part of Ni^{2+} ions
53 occupying octahedral sites and part of Al^{3+} ions tetrahedral ones [21]. On the other hand, the inversion
54 degree of spinels notably affects the nature of the surfaces and also their catalytic properties [22]. The
55 reduction step, indeed, can alter the structural properties. Thus, if metal-support interaction is
56 improved, a better catalytic behaviour could be obtained [23].

57 In the reduction process of spinel, the oxygen vacancies move through the spinel to the particle
58 surface. As a consequence, changes in the surface microstructure occur, with a major fraction of the
59 nickel metal particles forming on the surface. This way the creation of a nickel aluminate layer
60 between the metallic nickel particles and the alumina could prevent sintering [19]. It has been reported
61 that reduction at high temperatures promotes the rearrangement of nickel in the aluminate matrix, and
62 relatively small Ni crystallites with good textural stability can be obtained [23] what would imply a
63 significant advantage for catalytic applications. It has been reported that reduction of the nickel
64 aluminate leads to metallic Ni in strong interaction with alumina [24].

65 In this work nickel aluminate spinel was synthesized by coprecipitation at a stoichiometric nickel to
66 alumina mole ratio. It was activated at different reduction temperatures and the catalytic behaviour in
67 glycerol aqueous phase reforming was evaluated. Catalysts characterization was carried out by a wide
68 number of techniques (XRD, UV-visible-NIR DRS, FTIR, ^{27}Al MAS NMR, H_2 -TPR, H_2 -
69 chemisorption, CO_2 -TPD, NH_3 -TPD and TPO) and related to the catalytic performance. Adequate
70 nickel speciation and nickel-support interactions were sought in order to attain high selectivity to
71 hydrogen. To the best of our knowledge, the properties and the application of this catalytic system
72 for the glycerol aqueous phase reforming have not been yet investigated.

73 **2. Experimental**

74 2.1. Catalysts preparation

75 Bulk nickel aluminate (NiAl_2O_4) was synthesised by co-precipitation at a Ni/Al mole ratio of 1:2
76 (stoichiometric ratio). The procedure was as follows: proper amounts of nickel acetate (99.998% trace
77 metals basis, Sigma-Aldrich) and aluminium nitrate (98.0% purity, Fluka) aqueous solutions were
78 mixed in a vessel at ambient temperature. Aqueous ammonia was added to adjust pH at 8. Solution
79 was continuously stirred for 30 min, while the precipitated was formed. The suspension was kept at
80 ambient temperature for 30 min. The as-prepared solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with distilled

81 water at 90 °C, dried overnight at 110 °C and then calcined at 850 °C (heating rate 10 °C/min, hold 4
82 h). The as-prepared precursor was divided into six parts. Five were reduced at different temperatures
83 (300, 450, 600, 700 and 850 °C) and remaining part was no further modified. For the characterization
84 where in-situ reduction was not possible, the reduction was carried out ex-situ, in a quartz reactor,
85 under 5%H₂/He flow of 50 mL/min (heating at 10 °C/min, hold 1 h) from room temperature to the
86 desired temperature. Finally, sample was cooled down to room temperature in 5%H₂/He flow. The
87 reduced samples were labeled as NiAl-T, where T indicates the reduction temperature. The unreduced
88 sample was labeled as NiAl-c. Spent catalysts were named as NiAl-T-u (used for 2 h) or NiAl-T-50h
89 (after 50 h TOS). For comparative purposes, γ -alumina and NiO were also prepared by simple
90 calcination in air (at 850 °C) of aluminium nitrate and nickel acetate, respectively.

91 2.2. Characterization techniques

92 Bulk composition was determined by XRF (AXIOS, PANalytical), by using the fusion method. The
93 amount of leached metals was measured by ICP-AES in the overall liquid sample collected after each
94 reaction. The textural properties were obtained from the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms
95 determined at 77 K in Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020 equipment. Previously, each sample was
96 outgassed at 300 °C for 10 h, in order to remove moisture and carbon dioxide. The specific surface
97 area and the pore size distribution were determined by the BET and BJH methods, respectively.

98 The identification of crystalline phases and the morphological study was carried out by X-ray
99 diffraction conducted on a PANalytical Xpert PRO X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda =$
100 1.5418 Å). Scattered radiation was measured in the range $2\theta = 10-80^\circ$, with step size 0.026° and a
101 counting time of 2.5 s/step. The crystallite size of each species was estimated from its most intense
102 peak, by using the Scherrer equation. Crystalline phases present in the samples were identified by
103 comparing with the ICDD database.

104 Exposed metallic Ni atoms per catalyst gram and the Ni metallic surface area were calculated from
105 H₂ chemisorption, carried out in a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 equipment. Prior to analysis, the
106 samples were heated in He stream at 100 °C, and then reduced under 5% H₂/Ar flow for 2 h at the
107 corresponding reduction temperature. Then the sample was cooled down to 35 °C under Ar flow.
108 Then, H₂ pulses (loop volume 0.5312 mL) were injected until saturation. The exposed metal surface
109 area was calculated assuming H:Ni stoichiometry of 1:1 [25] and spherical Ni particles, with cross-
110 sectional area of 0.065 nm² and density of 8.9 cm³/g [26].

111 The reducibility of the prepared samples was studied by temperature-programmed reduction (H₂-
112 TPR) in a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument. For NiAl-c, about 70 mg of sample was initially
113 flushed in 5% O₂-He stream at 550 °C for 1 h (heated at 10 °C/ min). It was cooled down to room

114 temperature in Ar flow. Then, a flow of 5% H₂-Ar was passed through the bed containing the sample
115 while temperature was increased to 950 °C at 10 °C/min, and hold for 1 h. The H₂ consumption rate
116 was monitored in a previously calibrated thermal conductivity detector (TCD). The total H₂
117 consumption measured for sample NiAl-c was defined as TPR-a.

118 Also, H₂-TPR was carried out for the partially reduced samples (NiAl-T) in order to calculate the
119 fraction of reduced nickel ($f_{\text{Ni,red}}$). Firstly, approximately 70 mg of each sample was reduced at
120 temperature T, following the same protocol as for TPR-a. The amount of H₂ consumed in this stage
121 was defined as TPR-b. Then, it was cooled down to room temperature in He flow, and subsequent
122 TPR run, up to 950 °C, was carried out. The amount of H₂ consumed in this stage was defined as
123 TPR-c. The value $f_{\text{Ni,red}}$ for each NiAl-T sample was defined as the fraction of the amount of H₂
124 consumed during its reduction at temperature T (TPR-b) with respect to the total amount of H₂
125 consumed during the reduction of NiAl-c (TPR-a).

126 The speciation of nickel cations (coordination and oxidation states) was analysed by Diffuse
127 Reflectance UV-vis spectroscopy with a UV-vis-NIR Cary 5000 equipment coupled to Diffuse
128 Reflectance Internal 2500 within the range 200-2500 nm. Kubelka–Munk function was applied to
129 convert the DRS into equivalent absorption.

130 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) transmittance spectra were recorded in the 400-4000
131 cm⁻¹ range in a Cary 600 Series FTIR apparatus by employing KBr pellet technique, as an average of
132 50 scans with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

133 ²⁷Al Solid State NMR measurements were performed on a 9.4 T Bruker AVANCE III 400
134 spectrometer operating at resonance frequencies of 104.26 MHz for ²⁷Al. Chemical shifts were
135 referenced externally to the AlCl₃ aqueous solution at 0 ppm. The spectra were acquired at a spinning
136 frequency of 60 kHz employing a PH MASDVT400W BL 1.3mm ultrafast probehead. A single pulse
137 of 0.3 microseconds duration was applied and a recycle delay of 0.2 s and 36,000 scans were used.

138 Surface acidity and basicity were measured by NH₃ pulse chemisorption and CO₂ temperature
139 programmed desorption, respectively. Measurements were carried out in a Micromeritics AutoChem
140 2920 instrument coupled to Mass Spectroscopy (MKS, Cirrus 3000). About 35 mg of the calcined
141 precursor was initially pretreated in 5%O₂-He stream at 550 °C for 1 h (heating rate 10 °C/ min) and
142 cooled to room temperature. Then, it was reduced at the desired temperature in 5%H₂/Ar flow
143 (heating rate 10 °C/min), hold for 1 h and cooled down in He flow (to 90 °C for NH₃ adsorption and
144 to 40 °C for CO₂ adsorption). For acidity measurements, a series of 10% NH₃-He pulses (loop volume
145 0.5312 mL) were introduced at 90 °C until constant peak area was achieved. Then, temperature was
146 raised (10 °C/min) to 850 °C into He flow, and the released gases were monitored by MS (MKS

147 Cirrus) [27]. For basicity measurements, 5% CO₂/He flow was passed through the sample at 40 °C
148 up to saturation. Subsequently, the sample was exposed to a He flow for 60 min at 40 °C in order to
149 remove reversibly and physically bound CO₂. Finally, the temperature was raised to 900 °C (heating
150 rate 10 °C/min) and the resultant signal was followed by MS.

151 Carbon deposition on spent catalysts was evaluated by temperature-programmed oxidation (Setaram
152 Setsys evolution) coupled to mass spectroscopy (Pfeifer OmniStar) to follow the evolution of m/z
153 signals 44 (CO₂) and 18 (H₂O). Approximately 5 mg of calcium carbonate (used as reference) was
154 added to about 25 mg of sample. The mixture was treated under 5%O₂/He at 150 °C for 1 h and then
155 heated up to 1000 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min.

156 2.3. Catalytic performance evaluation

157 The aqueous phase reforming (APR) of glycerol was studied in a bench-scale fixed-bed up-flow
158 reactor (Microactivity Effi, PID Eng&TEch). The reactor (i.d. 5.1 mm, height 305 mm) was made of
159 Hastelloy alloy. In a typical run, about 0.5 g of catalyst (particle size 0.04-0.16 mm) were placed on
160 a stainless steel frit and covered with a quartz wool plug. Prior to reaction, it was reduced “in situ”,
161 at atmospheric pressure, under 20% H₂ flow (balance He) to the desired reduction temperature, T
162 (heating rate 5 °C/min), and hold for 1 h. Then, He flow was switched to bypass and 10 wt.% glycerol
163 (Panreac, >99.5% purity) aqueous solution was pumped into the reactor at 0.2 mL/min. Resultant
164 WHSV (determined as the ratio between feed mass-flowrate and mass of fresh catalyst) was of 24.5
165 h⁻¹. Catalytic performance was measured after two hours of operation. Three temperature/pressure
166 APR conditions were tested: 235 °C/35 bar, 250 °C/45 bar and 260 °C/52 bar. Reaction products were
167 cooled down to 5 °C. The gas products were swept with 40 mL/min of He flow introduced
168 immediately before backpressure regulator, and continuously analyzed by a GC-MS (μGC Agilent,
169 equipped with four columns (Al₂O₃-KCl 10 m, PPQ 10 m, MS5A 10 m, He as carrier and MS5A 10
170 m, Ar as carrier). The liquid products were analyzed off-line by GC-MS (Agilent, CP-Wax 57CB
171 column) and HPLC-RI (Waters, Hi-Plex H column). Total organic carbon (TOC) in the condensable
172 phase was measured on a Shimadzu TOC-5050A apparatus.

173 The total glycerol conversion (X_{Gly}) was calculated as follows:

$$174 \quad X_{Gly}(\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{Glycerol}^{in} - F_{Glycerol}^{out}}{F_{Glycerol}^{in}} \quad (4)$$

175 The carbon conversion to gas (X_{gas}) was calculated as follows:

$$176 \quad X_{gas}(\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{Catoms,feed}^{in} - F_{Catoms,liquid}^{out}}{F_{Catoms}^{in}} \quad (5)$$

177 Selectivity to gas (S_{gas}) was defined as the fraction of carbon moles converted into gas phase per
178 converted glycerol moles:

$$179 \quad S_{\text{gas}}(\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{Catoms,feed}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{Catoms,liquid}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{out}}} \times \frac{1}{3} \quad (6)$$

180 Hydrogen selectivity (S_{H_2}) was defined as the ratio between the moles of hydrogen produced and
181 moles of glycerol reacted, multiplied by 1/7 (inverse of the reforming glycerol/hydrogen ratio,
182 according to reaction (3):

$$183 \quad S_{\text{H}_2}(\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{H}_2}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{out}}} \times \frac{1}{7} \quad (7)$$

184 The selectivity of the C-containing product i was calculated as follows:

$$185 \quad S_i(\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_i^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{out}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{atoms},i}}{3} \quad (8)$$

186 Finally, hydrogen yield (Y_{H_2}) was defined as the ratio between the moles of hydrogen produced and
187 moles of glycerol fed into the reactor:

$$188 \quad Y_{\text{H}_2}(\%) = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{H}_2}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{Glycerol}}^{\text{in}}} \times \frac{1}{7} \quad (9)$$

189 3. Results and discussion

190 3.1. Materials characterization

191 3.1.1. Chemical composition and textural properties

192 The experimentally measured nickel loading was 31.3 wt.%, very close to the stoichiometric value
193 (33.2%). Textural properties, detailed in Table 1, revealed that specific surface area of nickel
194 aluminate NiAl-c was very similar to that of bare alumina (101.6 m²/g, Table S1, Supporting
195 Information). However, pore volume and average pore size (Table S1, Supporting Information)
196 increased more than two fold after incorporation of Ni. Type IV (IUPAC classification) isotherms
197 (Figure S1A, Supporting Information), characteristic of mesoporous solids, with H₂ hysteresis loop,
198 related to disordered porous materials were observed for the prepared assays, irrespective of the
199 reduction temperature. A slight increase in the pore volume, and average pore size (Table S1,
200 Supporting Information), occurred with increasing the reduction temperature. Concomitantly, surface
201 area slightly decreased (S_{BET} 98.0 m²/g for NiAl-c; 76.6 m²/g for NiAl-850), likely due to the phase
202 transformation from NiAl₂O₄ to Ni/Al₂O₃ [28,29] and the dilution effect. Also, partial blockage of
203 pores cannot be discarded. Overall, this behaviour pointed to a high structural stability of the
204 stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄. Pore size distribution (PSD) showed a unimodal structure for all samples

205 (Figure S1B, Supporting Information). It was observed that reduction at above 450 °C shifted PSD to
206 larger values, likely caused by the collapse of the smallest pores.

207 TABLE 1

208 3.1.2. H₂-TPR and H₂-chemisorption

209 The reducibility of the nickel aluminate spinel precursor (NiAl-c) and the partially reduced catalysts
210 (NiAl-T) was studied by temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR), and the obtained TPR profiles
211 are shown in Figure 1A. The reduction profile of NiO is also included for comparison. Note that TPR
212 profiles of NiAl-T samples corresponded to the so-called TPR-c, that is, the hydrogen consumption
213 profile of samples previously reduced at temperature T.

214 FIGURE 1

215 NiO exhibited a relatively narrow reduction peak in the 240 °C to 415 °C range, with its maximum at
216 377 °C. All Ni was reduced at below 400 °C as deduced from the experimentally measured hydrogen
217 consumption of 13.4 mmol_{H₂}/g (theoretical value 13.3 mmol_{H₂}/g). Bare γ -Al₂O₃ showed no H₂
218 consumption in the studied temperature range (not shown). It was clear that incorporation of
219 aluminium significantly modified the reduction profile of NiO. The observed shift in the reduction
220 profile of NiAl-c and that of the partially reduced catalysts evidenced the intimate interaction of Ni
221 with alumina. The left tail suggested the existence of a number of nickel species with different
222 reducibility. The H₂-TPR curve was split into peaks named α , β and γ , for the low, medium and high
223 temperature hydrogen consumption, respectively [30]. The α peak was ascribed to the reduction of
224 easily reducible surface free nickel oxide [30], formed in close interaction with the non-stoichiometric
225 nickel aluminate spinels [31]. The medium temperature β peak was ascribed to Ni²⁺ species in a
226 defective Ni_{1-x}Al₂O_{4-x} phase [32]. Finally, the high temperature peak (γ), centered at 837 °C, was
227 related to the reduction of Ni²⁺ species in the NiAl₂O₄ spinel lattice [24]. Free nickel oxide (α peak)
228 was reduced around 150 °C above that of bare NiO, what reflected the strong interaction between
229 NiO particles and the less reducible alumina [33].

230 Peak β was split into two contributions, namely β_1 (at lower temperature) and β_2 (at higher
231 temperature). The molar ratio β_1/β_2 for the non-reduced sample was 1.10, which, in turn, decreased
232 with the reduction temperature (Table 2). This suggested that composition of defective Ni_{1-x}Al₂O_{4-x}
233 depends upon reduction treatment, likely β_1 referred to Ni-rich solid and β_2 referred to Ni-lean solid
234 [34].

235 TABLE 2

236 Hydrogen consumption of β and γ species scarcely varied upon reduction below 450 °C, causing a
237 relative contribution to overall Ni species of around 45% and 52%, respectively. Reduction at 600 °C
238 decreased the hydrogen consumption of the defective spinel phase (β peak) to half, and for NiAl-700
239 sample Ni²⁺ species in the resultant catalyst were mainly as NiAl₂O₄. Eventually, at 850 °C, all Ni
240 added was fully reduced (Table 2, Figure 1A).

241 It has been suggested that reduction of α -type NiO produced large Ni particles [32,35]. The
242 quantitative results of the TPR profiles (Table 2) showed that α -type species were less than 2% for
243 the catalyst precursor studied here. Thus, the small average crystallite size of Ni⁰ particles obtained
244 (Table 1) could be partially attributed to the lack of "free" nickel oxide species and the fact that
245 catalyst precursor contained mainly Ni²⁺ species in spinel-like structure which favored dispersion of
246 the metallic nickel phase formed upon reduction.

247 Results from hydrogen pulse chemisorption are given in Table 2. As expected, the accessible metallic
248 nickel surface increased with the reduction temperature from 0.07 m²_{Ni}/g for NiAl-300 to 3.47 m²_{Ni}/g
249 for NiAl-850 (in terms of exposed Ni atoms it increased from 1.14·10¹⁸ for NiAl-300 to 53.4·10¹⁸
250 at_{Ni}/g for NiAl-850), as due to the migration of nickel from spinel phase to the catalyst surface. As
251 shown by TPR, diffusion of Ni²⁺ commenced at around 600 °C (also discussed in XRD and ²⁷Al NMR
252 sections).

253 3.1.3. XRD characterization

254 The most prominent features of XRD patterns are ascribed to cubic spinel structure (JCPDS 78-1601)
255 (Figure 2A). Diffraction line at $2\theta=65.6^\circ$ (plane (440)) confirmed the formation of NiAl₂O₄ spinel.
256 NiO was not detected, probably, because of the smaller than detection limit (2-5 nm) size of the
257 crystallites. Characteristic features of metallic nickel appeared upon reduction at 600 °C or above (2θ
258 = 44.5°, 51.8° and 76.4°) (JCPDS 01-087-0712), and increased in intensity with reduction
259 temperature. It was observed that reduction at ≤ 600 °C hardly altered the XRD spectra peak shape
260 and position (i.e. $2\theta = 19.0, 37.0$ and 59.6° remained almost constant) reflecting the high stability of
261 the NiAl₂O₄ phase. Although TPR analysis confirmed that about 6% of the nickel in the spinel
262 precursor was reduced at 450 °C, its absence in the XRD spectra highlighted an adequate dispersion
263 of the metal. The formation of γ -alumina phase (JCPDS 79-1558) could be recognized upon reduction
264 at 850 °C.

265 From a structural perspective, the experimentally measured lattice parameter for the unreduced
266 sample was 8.044 Å (Table S2, Supporting Information), very close to that of stoichiometric nickel
267 aluminate spinel (8.0451 Å) [21]. Values of lattice parameter decreased with reduction temperature.
268 This lattice compression reflected the migration of the nickel ions from the nickel aluminate lattice

269 to the surface, suggesting that the solid bulk was progressively enriched in alumina. Upon reduction,
270 metallic nickel crystallized into *Fm-3m* cubic system (JCPDS 01-087-0712). No evidence was found
271 for hexagonal close packed nickel. At the highest reduction temperature of 850 °C, 2 θ position for
272 plane (440) shifted to 67.3° (given as $\Delta\theta$ in Figure S2, Supporting Information), reinforcing the idea
273 that nickel was drawn towards Ni clusters and matrix composition tended to γ -Al₂O₃ [29].

274 The intensity ratio of peaks corresponding to (220) and (440) reticular planes (I_{220} / I_{440}) (Table S2,
275 Supporting Information) varied among the prepared catalysts. The intensity ratio I_{220} / I_{440} was related
276 to cation distribution [36]. As the ionic radius of Ni²⁺ cation (0.69 Å) exceeds that of Al³⁺ (0.54 Å),
277 I_{220} / I_{440} increases with increasing Ni²⁺ cations on tetrahedral sites (T_d), and the ratio decreases with
278 increasing occupancy of Ni²⁺ cations on octahedral sites (Oh). For “normal” spinel this ratio would
279 approximate to 0.33. We measured a value of 0.25 for NiAl-c (Table S2, Supporting Information),
280 and a decreasing trend with reduction temperature (i.e. $I_{220} / I_{440} = 0.21$ for sample NiAl-700) was
281 observed. That is, the reduced system was slightly enriched in Ni²⁺ cations hosted in octahedral sites.
282 Therefore, we might conclude that tetrahedral Ni²⁺ cations were more readily reduced as compared
283 to octahedral Ni²⁺ sites. Presumably, the lattice oxide ions of the trigonal prism stabilize the Ni²⁺ ion
284 rather effectively.

285 FIGURE 2

286 Crystallite size of nickel aluminate and metallic nickel (in reduced catalysts) varied in the 9-10 nm
287 and 8-14 nm range, respectively (Table 1). In both cases, no clear trend in crystal growth was observed
288 with the reduction temperature. The relatively small size of the metallic nickel nanoclusters formed
289 in our system, in spite of the high reduction temperature, reflected the strong interaction of nickel
290 with the Ni-Al-O support, which stabilized Ni particles and reduced their surface mobility, protecting
291 against the sinterisation under reductive atmosphere [32,34]. For instance, Ni/alumina catalysts
292 prepared by wet impregnation, and at a similar nickel content, showed a metallic nickel crystallite
293 size of about 26 nm [37].

294 3.1.4. Skeletal DRS UV-vis NIR and IR characterization

295 Figure 3 shows the diffuse reflectance UV-vis NIR spectra of the prepared samples. Main features of
296 NiO spectra include the broad bands in the 900-1400 nm and 250-350 nm regions, ascribed to O²⁻ →
297 Ni²⁺ charge transfers [38] and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) transition bands at 377, 414 and at 720 nm. All these
298 features are characteristic of octahedral Ni²⁺ in NiO lattice [39]. For catalyst NiAl-c, the intensity in
299 the O²⁻ → Ni²⁺ charge transfers region increased whereas it was attenuated in the visible range, at
300 around 720 nm, what suggested that Ni²⁺ cations existed in a different electronic environment as
301 compared to bare NiO. The intense doublet, with maxima at 605 and 638 nm, observed for catalyst

302 NiAl-c, was attributed to the ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_2$ (3P) spin-allowed transition of Ni^{2+} ions in tetrahedral
303 symmetry (Ni^{2+}_{Td}). Moreover, absorption bands centered at 550 and 760 nm characteristic of Ni^{2+}_{Td}
304 were clearly observed. Thus, these results reflected that Ni^{2+} ions were embedded in the alumina
305 lattice to form $NiAl_2O_4$ phase in the non-reduced NiAl-c sample, in accordance with XRD data.

306 The DRS UV-vis NIR spectra of partially reduced samples (i.e. ≤ 450 °C) were qualitatively similar
307 to NiAl-c. Reduction at 600 °C removed typical features of NiO and nickel aluminate and only some
308 complex bands at around 330 nm were observed, ascribed to metallic nickel nanoparticles [40].

309 The intensity ratio of the doublet at 600-650 nm to peak at 1100 nm ($Ni^{2+}_{Td}/Ni^{2+}_{Oh}$) was used to
310 measure the relative content of Ni^{2+}_{Td} with respect to Ni^{2+}_{Oh} [41]. The experimentally measured
311 values (Table S2, Supporting Information) reflected that the highest $Ni^{2+}_{Td}/Ni^{2+}_{Oh}$ corresponded to
312 sample NiAl-c, and decreased upon reduction, what supports the XRD data.

313

FIGURE 3

314 Further structural characterization carried out by FTIR analysis (Figure S3, Supporting Information)
315 confirmed the above observations. Spinel structure was identified in sample calcined at 850 °C which
316 was readily transformed into γ -alumina under H_2 flow. In the FTIR spectra, alumina could be detected
317 upon reduction above 600 °C (Figure S3A, Supporting Information)

318 3.1.5. ${}^{27}Al$ MAS NMR

319 Figure 4A shows the ${}^{27}Al$ MAS NMR spectra of NiAl-T samples. The spectrum of $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ consisted
320 of two peaks at 3.7 and 60 ppm (i.e. octahedral and tetrahedral aluminium, respectively), with an
321 intensity ratio of 73:27, as also reported by others [42].

322 The non-reduced assay showed a broad peak centered at -33 ppm, reflecting the predominant
323 existence of Al_{Oh} . The subtle peak at around 70 ppm denoted the presence of Al_{Td} , characteristic of
324 partially inverted spinels. Reduction at below 600 °C hardly varied the Al-NMR spectra, and Al^{3+}
325 mainly occupied the octahedral sites. However, reduction at above 600 °C increased the amount of
326 Al_{Td} in the catalyst, as deduced from the enlarged signal at around 60 ppm. This is consistent with
327 the departure of Ni^{2+} to octahedral sites to ensure neutrality. Indeed, Figure 4B shows that Al_{Oh}
328 chemical shift linearly increased with the reduction temperature, which was bottom and upper limited
329 by NiAl-c (-33.3 ppm) and γ -alumina (+3.8 ppm). For NiAl-850 sample, $\delta_{Al_{Oh}}$ was +0.8 ppm, close
330 to γ -alumina.

331

FIGURE 4

332 3.1.6. Surface acidity and basicity

333 Aqueous phase reforming of glycerol involves, among others, dehydration reactions [15], which are
334 very sensitive to catalysts surface acid-base properties [43]. Therefore, the study of the total amount
335 and strength of such functionalities could help the interpretation of the activity and selectivity data.
336 Results from CO₂ and NH₃ chemisorption are given in Table 1 and Figure 5.

337 Activation under hydrogen flow increased acidity, up to 35% (highest value for NiAl-850: 2.13
338 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3}/\text{m}^2$). The increase of surface basicity was even more marked, up to a two-fold increase,
339 especially at the most severe reduction conditions. The fact that strong sites decreased during
340 reduction suggested that exposed coordinatively unsaturated nickel cations and oxygen species in the
341 calcined spinel may act as strong acid and basic sites, respectively. Treatment under hydrogen flow
342 caused surface enrichment in medium strength sites. This was probably due to the progressive
343 dehydroxylation of the surface and increase of exposed γ -alumina on surface, as revealed by XRD,
344 FTIR and ²⁷Al MAS NMR. Actually, reduction at above 600 °C completely removed strong sites.
345 Moreover, it has been reported that reduced Ni could react with strong acid sites and generate Ni²⁺
346 ions (as NiO), which increase the middle-strength acidity [44]. The observed complexity in the
347 medium strength desorption region as reduction temperature increased (Figure S4, Supporting
348 Information) could be ascribed to modification of the oxygen coordination in the catalyst surface.
349 Overall, based on the APR selectivity data discussed later, it can be deemed that these differences in
350 the acid-base properties were sufficient to change catalyst performance.

351

FIGURE 5

352 3.1.7. General overview of the catalysts physico-chemical properties upon reduction

353 Nickel species of different reducibility were found in the nearly stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄ prepared by
354 coprecipitation: (i) a small fraction of surface free nickel oxide, without interaction with the support,
355 which vanishes after reduction above 300 °C; (ii) two kinds of Ni²⁺ species in defective Ni_{1-x}Al₂O_{4-x}
356 (one in Ni-rich and the other in Al-rich environment) which contribution decreased upon reduction at
357 above 600 °C; and (iii) nickel in spinel phase, which can only be completely reduced at 850 °C or
358 above. Based on H₂-TPR data, Ni²⁺ species in Ni-rich mixed oxide phase (peak β_1), were more
359 reducible [29]. Reduced Ni²⁺ species migrated to the solid surface leading to a framework enriched
360 in Ni²⁺ species in Al-rich mixed oxide phase (β_2), as suggested by the decrease of the β_1/β_2 ratio
361 (Table 2).

362 Under H₂ atmosphere, nickel diffused through the lattice of the non-stoichiometric spinel to form
363 metallic Ni (Table 2). Ni diffusion continued until Ni_{1-x}Al₂O_{4-x} was completely reduced, at around
364 700 °C. Above that temperature, further Ni diffusion proceeded from stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄. A

365 similar behaviour was observed by Braidy et al. [34] with Ni doped alumina spinels prepared by wet-
366 incipient method. They proposed that under reductive atmosphere, a continuous transition between
367 $\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{4-x}$ towards γ -alumina occurs as Ni leaves the matrix to form NiAl_2O_4 and eventually Ni.
368 The intermediate formation of NiAl_2O_4 before metallic Ni, could explain the observed upturn in the
369 contribution of NiAl_2O_4 in the NiAl-T series (Table 2). Previous research [24, 29], based on H_2 -TPR
370 analyses, concluded that Ni located in tetrahedral sites could be more difficult to reduce than Ni
371 located in octahedral sites. Nevertheless, based on XRD, DRS-UV-vis and ^{27}Al -NMR data of our
372 stoichiometric nickel aluminate spinels a different behaviour could be evidenced. That is, upon
373 reduction, the number of tetrahedral nickel atoms diminished and increased that in octahedral sites).
374 Regarding surface acid/basic properties, treatment under hydrogen flow caused surface enrichment
375 in medium strength sites.

376 3.2. Catalytic performance experiments

377 Catalytic APR tests were performed at 250 °C/45 bar in a bench-scale fixed-bed up-flow reactor. Bare
378 γ -alumina and NiAl-c showed null activity (not shown). Blank tests with the reactor bed filled with
379 quartz wool (employed to keep the bed fixed) showed no glycerol conversion, which suggested that
380 homogeneous APR had no contribution to the catalytic conversion of glycerol. As a reference, the
381 activity of bare Ni (obtained by reduction of NiO at 700 °C for 1 h) was also evaluated.

382 Glycerol conversion (X_{Gly}) and carbon conversion to gas (X_{gas}) of NiAl-T catalysts in-situ reduced at
383 temperature T are displayed in Figure 6A. Aqueous phase reforming of glycerol was negligible by
384 reduced bare Ni catalysts which did not surpass conversion values of 3%. Raney Ni has been reported
385 to be active for APR [45]. The very low performance of our bare nickel catalyst (in terms of X_{Gly} and
386 X_{gas}) could be ascribed to its low surface area (less than 5 m^2/g).

387 Similarly, values for NiAl-350 and NiAl-450 remained below 5%. However, catalytic activity notably
388 increased by increasing the catalysts' reduction temperature from 450 °C to 600 °C. For instance,
389 glycerol conversion increased by a factor of 20 (NiAl-600: $X_{\text{Gly}} = 66\%$). The most active assay was
390 that reduced at 850 °C with $X_{\text{Gly}} = 93\%$ (i.e. X_{Gly} increased by a factor of 1.4 with respect to
391 NiAl-600). In addition, reduction at the highest temperature had a positive effect on the formation of
392 gaseous products. The selectivity to gas (S_{gas}), that is, the percentage of carbon moles converted into
393 gas phase per converted glycerol moles, was doubled in this temperature range: NiAl-600 (31%);
394 NiAl-850 (62%), Figure 6A. Concomitantly, the exposed Ni metallic area increased by a factor of 5
395 (Table 2), $\text{NiAl-600}/\text{NiAl-450} = 0.48/0.10$). Thus, the role of the available Ni^0 in the reforming
396 activity seemed evident. At this point, it is interesting to note that the specific rate of hydrogen
397 production, defined as the rate of hydrogen production per accessible nickel area, was maximum for

398 NiAl-600 (Figure 6B), which could be ascribed to its smallest metallic particle size (Table 1). It has
399 been reported that partial oxidation of the surface of catalyst and the presence of metal oxide can
400 facilitate dehydrogenation reactions [46]. Regarding particle size, both reforming and WGS reactions
401 involve activation of water molecule. Alumina is able to activate water by forming hydroxyl groups.
402 Nickel, in contrast to other metals such as Pt [47], is also capable of activating water via NiO
403 formation [48]. Therefore, reactive Ni sites should be in close proximity to alumina, what would be
404 more feasible over the smallest Ni particles.

405 FIGURE 6

406 TABLE 3

407 Data on Table 3 provide a comparison of the catalytic performance of our samples and others reported
408 in the literature. In general terms, it is remarkable the high performance shown by our nickel
409 aluminate catalysts when comparing with other nickel-based catalysts, in spite of the high space
410 velocity (WHSV 24.5 h⁻¹) employed. The performance in terms of activity of our catalysts was even
411 comparable to Pt-based catalysts, though, at lower selectivity to hydrogen, due to the inherent
412 methanation activity of Ni. Indeed, it would be of interest to focus future research on increasing the
413 selectivity to hydrogen (decrease selectivity to alkanes) of nickel aluminate-based catalytic system.

414 3.2.1. Gas phase products

415 The main products in the gas phase were hydrogen, carbon dioxide and methane, which accounted
416 for more than 97% of the reaction products (in mol %), for all catalysts. Other minor compounds
417 detected in the gas phase were alkanes (ethane, propane and C₄₊) and carbon monoxide. Molar flow
418 of gaseous products by catalysts NiAl-300 and NiAl-450 was very low, around 30 times lower than
419 most active assays (Figure 7). The former catalysts produced a gas stream mainly composed by
420 hydrogen (80-90% H₂). However, due to their low activity, because active sites are known to be the
421 metallic nickel sites, hydrogen yield was very low (Y_{H₂}= 0.7-1.4%, Table 4). For the catalysts reduced
422 at 600 °C or above, hydrogen yield notably increased (up to 21%) what, subsequently, favoured
423 hydrogenolysis and hydrogenation reactions [56], as discussed in the liquid products section.
424 Consequently, hydrogen concentration in the gas stream decreased, and levelled-off, at around 40-
425 50% with a moderate formation of methane (i.e. 22%). It seems interesting to note that activity
426 increased with reduction temperature in the 600 °C to 850 °C interval (i.e. amount of active sites
427 increased, Table 2), however, the gas phase composition remained quite similar (Figure 7), what
428 suggests that reaction mechanism did not vary substantially among the most active assays.

429 FIGURE 7

430 TABLE 4

431 The C-C scission ability of nickel was clearly evidenced from the large difference observed in the
432 selectivity of C₁ (methane) and C₂ + C₃ alkanes (Table 4, Figure S5, Supporting Information), which
433 implies that C-C scission activity was higher than dehydration/hydrogenation of the intermediate
434 liquid compounds [57]. These results also suggested that a minimum amount of metallic Ni was
435 required on catalyst surface to drive hydrogenolysis reactions. The metallic sites would ensure
436 sufficient in-situ produced hydrogen for the hydrogenation of the liquid intermediate hydroxyacetone
437 molecule. For instance, catalyst NiAl-450, with 0.1 m²_{Ni}/g, mainly produced C₃ alkanes. This sample
438 presented the highest acid to basic sites ratio (4.9, Table 1) which is beneficial for cleavage of C-O
439 bonds [58]. However, catalyst NiAl-600 (~0.5 m²_{Ni}/g) showed a selectivity of 17% to C₁ alkane
440 (methane), with negligible formation of C₂ and C₃ alkanes. According to reaction network proposed
441 (Scheme 1), methane was formed by CO hydrogenation, which requires metallic sites. The formation
442 of methane was thermodynamically favoured, as CO hydrogenation reaction to methane is
443 exothermic. As revealed by data in Table 4, H₂/CO₂ ratio remained below 7/3 (stoichiometric ratio in
444 APR of glycerol) and decreased with reduction temperature. Indeed, this result supports that hydrogen
445 was readily used in parallel reactions. Decarbonylation of intermediate liquid organic compounds
446 formed CO molecules, which undergo WGS reaction to produce CO₂ and H₂ (Scheme 1). Indeed, Ni-
447 based catalysts are reported to be active for the WGS reaction [59]. The low amount of CO obtained
448 with our samples (Table 4) suggested that WGS was also favoured by NiAl₂O₄-derived catalysts to
449 form H₂ and CO₂. C₂ and higher alkanes could be formed through Fischer-Tropsch [8] and other
450 reactions. For example, dehydration/hydrogenation of light alcohols can produce ethane and propane,
451 while condensation reactions of intermediate liquid products can yield butane [60].

452 3.2.2. Liquid phase products

453 Molar flow of liquid products was negligible for catalysts NiAl-300 and NiAl-450, as well as for bare
454 Ni, as due to their low catalytic activity. Catalyst reduced at 600 °C produced around 0.7
455 mmolC/g_{cat}·min of intermediate liquid products, which slightly decreased by increasing the reduction
456 temperature (i.e. 0.53 mmolC/g_{cat}·min for NiAl-850) (Figure 8A). This decline was ascribed to
457 gasification of intermediate oxygenated hydrocarbon species by reforming reactions [8,61], as
458 deduced from the concomitant increase in the conversion to gas.

459 FIGURE 8

460 SCHEME 1

461 The reaction network (Scheme 1) for the glycerol APR over bifunctional NiAl-T catalysts comprises
462 two main routes: dehydrogenation to glyceraldehyde (route A), which requires metal sites, and
463 dehydration to hydroxyacetone (route B), which requires acid sites. It is widely accepted that

464 hydroxyacetone is formed by elimination of primary hydroxyl group of glycerol, while
465 3-hydroxypropanal is formed by elimination of secondary hydroxyl group [62]. The fact that the later
466 was no detected, was ascribed to the preponderant Lewis type acidity of our solids [62].

467 According to Figure 8A, the catalyst activation temperature strongly affected the selectivity to the
468 liquid products. Catalysts reduced at low temperature (NiAl-300 and NiAl-450) mainly produced
469 hydroxyacetone and very low amounts of small chain mono-alcohols (ethanol, methanol), suggesting
470 that these catalysts favour dehydration reactions, as due to the scarcity of accessible nickel surface.
471 The acid function was dominant in these catalysts (as revealed by a high ratio of acid/base sites).
472 Consequently, hydroxyacetone was hardly hydrogenated to propylene glycol. In contrast, bare Ni,
473 with only metallic function, produced a liquid stream mainly composed by methanol (73%) and an
474 hydrogen-rich gaseous stream. According to Scheme 1, methanol was formed through
475 decarbonylation reactions (route A), with CO (and H₂) release, which would be subsequently
476 converted by WGS to yield more hydrogen and CO₂.

477 For catalysts reduced at 600 °C or above, the main liquid products were glycols (1,2-propylene glycol
478 and ethylene glycol), small chain mono-alcohols (ethanol and methanol), hydroxyacetone and,
479 acetaldehyde in much lesser concentration. The observed liquid products distribution pointed to a
480 complex process, where dehydrogenation, dehydration and hydrogenolysis reactions take place [6].

481 It should be noted that large amounts of glycols (sum of ethylene glycol and 1,2-propylene glycol)
482 were produced, in the 47-59% range (Figure 8A), by all the active assays, indicative of C-O (i.e. 1,3-
483 propylene glycol) and C-H and C-C (i.e. ethylene glycol) bond scission over Ni sites. Small amounts
484 of 1-propanol and 2-propanol were also detected (less than 2%). These can be produced by additional
485 dehydration and hydrogenation of 1,2-propylene glycol in the presence of hydrogen [63].

486 Liquid phase product distribution was notably affected by the catalyst activation temperature.
487 Production of 1,2-propylene glycol and hydroxyacetone decreased as reduction temperature increased
488 (1,2-propylene glycol: from 44% to 29%; hydroxyacetone: from 16% to 7%, both cases by NiAl-600
489 and NiAl-850, respectively). In contrast, the production of methanol and ethanol increased in similar
490 intensity.

491 Figure 8B shows the evolution of the overall reaction products of route A with respect to all reaction
492 products of route B. That is, the sum of total products of dehydrogenation (methanol, ethylene glycol
493 and ethanol) and dehydration (hydroxyacetone and 1,2-propylene glycol) reactions are depicted. A
494 clear trend could be observed where an increase in the reduction temperature enhanced the production
495 of dehydrogenation products. In contrast, a concomitant decrease of dehydration/hydrogenation
496 products could be confirmed. For instance, for catalysts reduced at below 600 °C

497 dehydration/hydrogenation products accounted for 39% of APR products, which increased up to 61%
498 at the highest reduction temperature. From Figure 8B it could be concluded that at above 700 °C,
499 route A prevailed. This confirms the relevant role of metallic sites in determining the dominant route
500 in the APR of glycerol. The fact that route A (dehydrogenation-decarbonylation) was the main
501 mechanism reflected that C-H and C-C scission by hydrogenolysis was favoured, in detriment of C-O
502 cleavage, as also reported by others [64]. Gandarias et al. [65] studied the effect of the incorporation
503 of Cu into Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts. They concluded that the reduction in size of the Ni ensembles inhibited
504 the C-C bond cleavage. This effect should not be discarded for our catalytic system.

505 The formation of Ni-C bond requires a previous dehydrogenation of glycerol in order to be adsorbed
506 on Ni metal [64]. The high selectivity to hydroxyacetone suggested that this mechanism prevailed for
507 catalyst NiAl-300 and NiAl-450, probably due to its low hydrogen yield. If hydrogen partial pressure
508 increases (i.e. due to in-situ formation), both hydrogen and glycerol can adsorb on Ni sites. Then,
509 after protonation of hydroxyl group by metallic acidic sites [66], the cleavage of C-O bond would
510 proceed followed by hydrogen transfer from Ni to the carbon, resulting in 1,2-propylene glycol
511 formation, which was observed for catalysts reduced at 600 °C or above. The occurrence of this route
512 would be supported by the presence of propanols, which were formed through the
513 dehydration/hydrogenation of 1,2-propylene glycol (Scheme 1). However, the small amounts of
514 propanols and acetone (less than 0.8 mol%) reflected the 1,2-propylene glycol was the final liquid
515 product by this route, since further decomposition would require acid sites for dehydration to acetone
516 or propionaldehyde. Experimental data pointed to the preponderance of metallic function with respect
517 to acid function in the investigated catalytic system.

518 Ethanol can be formed through hydrogenation of the acetaldehyde molecule [67] (Scheme 1). The
519 low amount of acetaldehyde produced by our active catalysts revealed the feasibility of this route. By
520 increasing reduction temperature, H₂/CO₂ ratio slightly decreased, as shown in Table 4, as the yield
521 to ethanol increased. This result suggested that for catalysts reduced at the highest temperatures (700
522 and 850 °C) hydrogen yield increased, however, a larger fraction of the in-situ formed hydrogen was
523 consumed in hydrogenolysis reactions. Catalyst NiAl-850 showed to be the best catalyst in terms of
524 glycerol conversion and hydrogen yield for the aqueous phase reforming of 10 wt.% glycerol.
525 However, it seems interesting to note that the intrinsic activity of the Ni active sites was largest for
526 NiAl-600 (Figure 6B). It could be concluded that catalyst reduced at the highest temperature
527 consumed more hydrogen in parallel reactions with superior methane formation. It would be of
528 interest to gain knowledge on the properties required to improve the intrinsic activity of the catalyst
529 reduced at the highest temperature. It is likely that adequate surface acid/base properties of the nickel

530 aluminate catalyst could allow tuning the selectivity towards dehydrogenation reactions rather than
531 hydrogenolysis.

532 3.2.3. Effect of working Temperature/Pressure conditions

533 Catalytic tests were performed at 235 °C/35 bar, 250 °C/45 bar and 260 °C/52 bar over in-situ reduced
534 NiAl-T catalysts. As shown in Figure 9A (and Table S3, Supporting Information), independent of the
535 operation conditions, activity was negligible for catalysts NiAl-350 and NiAl-450, which did not
536 surpass conversion values of 5%. The performance of the rest of catalysts, in terms of conversion of
537 glycerol and gasification activity, improved at the most severe APR conditions, in agreement with
538 literature [13,46]. For example, X_{gas} increased by 31% (NiAl-450), 63% (NiAl-600), 74% (NiAl-700)
539 and 79% (NiAl-850) by changing from 235 °C/35 bar to 260 °C/52 bar. Concomitantly, S_{gas} increased
540 by 22% (NiAl-600), 30% (NiAl-700) and 38% (NiAl-850). Hydrogen yield also increased (Table S3,
541 Supporting Information), due to enhanced C-C and C-O bond cleavage promoted by temperature
542 increase [68,69].

543 Apparent activation energy was estimated assuming first order reaction kinetics. The obtained values
544 (Figure 9A), ranged between 75-110 kJ/mol, reflecting the weight of catalyst configuration on
545 reaction mechanism. The increasing trend in the E_a suggests that the reactions over metallic nickel
546 sites were characterized by a higher activation energy than those occurring over the acid sites.

547 FIGURE 9

548 The concentration of H_2 and CH_4 in the gas stream (Table S3, Supporting Information) slightly varied
549 with T/P conditions, and a trade-off could be deduced between both species. This way, as T/P varied
550 from 235 °C/35 bar to 260 °C/52 bar, the H_2 concentration in the gas stream vaguely decreased: 54%
551 to 52% (NiAl-600); 53% to 45% (NiAl-700); 48% to 43% (NiAl-850), while CH_4 concentration
552 increased as: 20% to 21% (NiAl-600); 19% to 24% (NiAl-700); 20% to 25% (NiAl-850).
553 Accordingly, H_2/CO_2 ratio declined (Table S3, Supporting Information) what reflected hydrogen
554 consumption in parallel reactions, such as CO methanation, as revealed by increased selectivity to
555 methane.

556 The alkane selectivity as a function of C number followed similar distribution with reaction T/P, the
557 highest selectivity being for C1 alkanes (methane) for the three T/P operation conditions (Figure S5,
558 Supporting Information). At most severe conditions selectivity to methane increased, especially at
559 the highest reduction temperature.

560 Liquid phase composition of active catalysts also varied with the reaction T/P conditions (Figure 9B),
561 while for catalyst NiAl-450 it was almost unaffected. Moreover, the effect of T/P became more
562 intense as reduction temperature increased (i.e. the activation energy). A trade-off between small

563 chain alcohols (which increased) and glycols (which decreased) was observed with the increase of
564 T/P, with almost constant formation of hydroxyacetone.

565 The ratio between overall reaction products of route A with respect to route B was above 1 for
566 NiAl-700 and NiAl-850 catalysts, and below 1 for the rest of catalysts. In addition, it increased with
567 reaction T/P conditions, except for NiAl-450 (Figure S6, Supporting Information). For example,
568 changing from 235 °C/35 bar to 260 °C/52 bar, it increased from 1.1 to 2.9 for NiAl-850 catalyst, and
569 at lesser extent for NiAl-600 (from 0.5 to 0.7). This behaviour could be interpreted as that most severe
570 conditions favoured decarbonylation and C-C scission over C-O scission [70].

571 3.2.4. Long-term experiments

572 Catalytic performance (i.e. glycerol conversion, conversion to gas and selectivity to gas) as a function
573 of time-on-stream (TOS) was investigated for catalysts NiAl-700 and NiAl-850, under mild
574 conditions (235 °C/35 bar) for a period of 50 h. As shown in Figure 10 both catalysts followed a
575 similar trend, with a sustained loss of activity over the whole catalytic test, being more pronounced
576 during the first hours of operation (i.e. 8 h TOS). An overall decay of around 45% and 60% was
577 observed in the glycerol conversion and conversion to gas, respectively. S_{gas} also decreased with TOS,
578 and after 20 h, it levelled-off at around 61% and 73% for NiAl-700 and NiAl-850, respectively. The
579 stability of these catalysts can be deemed as good as compared to other nickel supported catalysts.
580 For example, Shabaker et al. [45] reported 90% of initial activity decay during 48 hours of APR of
581 ethylene glycol over Ni supported on different supports, among them γ -alumina, and attributed to
582 metal sintering. Thus, catalysts prepared by activation of spinel-based precursors showed promising
583 stability results, as compared to traditional impregnation methods.

584

FIGURE 10

585 Figure 11 depicts the evolution with TOS of several reaction parameters related to the selectivity of
586 the APR reaction of NiAl-700 and NiAl-850 catalysts. Selectivity to hydrogen increased, particularly
587 after 20-30 h of TOS. The yield to hydrogen, however, remained stable due to the counter effect of
588 the loss of activity. Concomitantly, selectivity to methane decreased as reaction proceeded, particularly
589 for NiAl-700 (Figures 11A and B).

590 The total molar flow of gaseous products dropped-off by around 26% for both catalysts after 50 h of
591 operation. The gas stream enriched in hydrogen with TOS, and both H_2/CO_2 and H_2/CH_4 ratios
592 increased (Figures 11A and B). The opposite trend was observed on H_2/CO , especially for catalyst
593 NiAl-700. H_2/CO decreased by around 36% for catalyst NiAl-850 and up to 65% for NiAl-700. This
594 is consistent with a limited occurrence of WGS as TOS increased. It is known the high CO and CO_2
595 hydrogenation [71] and WGS [47] activity of metallic Ni. In both reactions, the C-containing

596 molecule is firstly activated onto the metallic site [72]. The observed data suggested that the severe
597 hydrothermal conditions of APR inhibit the CO activation capacity of Ni. The fact that NiAl-700
598 contained half the amount of Ni⁰ of NiAl-850 would make it more sensitive to deactivation.

599 FIGURE 11

600 Regarding intermediate liquid products, both NiAl-700 and NiAl-850 showed similar trend, where
601 hydroxyacetone formation increased and ethylene glycol, ethanol and methanol decreased with TOS
602 (Figure 11C). This behaviour revealed a decreasing trend in the (Scheme 1) route A/route B product
603 distribution, which varied from 1.1 to 0.7 for NiAl-700 and from 0.85 to 0.6 for NiAl-850, indicative
604 of a loss of metal function.

605 3.3. Characterization of spent catalysts

606 The spent catalysts were analysed in order to elucidate the main factors that contribute to catalyst
607 deactivation. The nickel re-oxidation and lixiviation, the structural changes in the catalysts and the
608 formation of carbonaceous deposits were analysed.

609 The specific surface area of the spent catalysts increased (Table 1), more markedly for samples
610 reduced at higher temperature. The used samples showed bimodal pore size distribution (Figure S1B,
611 Supporting Information), which would be related to the coexistence of both boehmite and nickel
612 aluminate phases.

613 H₂-TPR analysis of spent NiAl-T catalysts (named as NiAl-T-u) are shown in Figure 1B, and the
614 obtained values are given in Table S4, Supporting Information. Catalysts NiAl-300-u showed an
615 incipient peak below 500 °C, indicative of nickel re-oxidation. Samples reduced at T ≥ 600 °C showed
616 a substantial low-temperature hydrogen consumption what reflected that re-oxidation of metallic Ni
617 took place to a greater extent. Reduction at 250 °C suggested coalescence into large NiO particles as
618 due to high free surface energy. The less intense, unresolved peaks in the 300-600 °C range observed
619 for samples NiAl-700 and NiAl-850 were ascribed to the reduction of smaller NiO particles
620 interacting with the support or to nickel defective spinel compounds. The subtle reduction peak of
621 catalyst NiAl-850 at about 750 °C suggested that part of the Ni was re-oxidized to the original spinel
622 structure, facilitated by the open spinel structure of γ -alumina that hosted the Ni²⁺ species [73]. TPR
623 analyses quantified this amount at around 4.2% of the loaded Ni. Note that the high temperature
624 hydrogen consumption (at around 775 °C) of NiAl-700 indicated the existence of nickel aluminate
625 spinel, yet unreduced in the fresh catalyst. For these most active catalysts, overall, around 45% of the
626 metallic Ni in fresh catalyst was re-oxidised (Table 2). Yet, we have no clear evidence to explain the
627 larger than 100% re-oxidation measured for catalyst NiAl-600. We hypothesize it could be caused by
628 leaching of Ni atoms located in the spinel structure, and subsequent re-deposition on the surface [37].

629 [74] employed Ni/alumina prepared by wetness impregnation for the ethylene glycol reforming, and
630 also acknowledged the nickel oxidation as the main cause of deactivation.

631 The reduction profiles of catalysts used for 50 h (NiAl-700-50h and NiAl-850-50h, Figure 1B) were
632 qualitatively very similar to those used for 2 h. In the spent catalyst, around 34% of the initial Ni was
633 re-oxidized, what indicated that most of the metallic Ni in our catalytic system was oxidized during
634 initial stages of APR. This would explain the previously noted initial fast activity decay (Figure 10).
635 Thereafter, these species were progressively leached out, and around 7% of the metal loaded was lost
636 during the long-term catalytic run (Table 1).

637 XRD analysis of the used samples revealed the presence of boehmite phase (Figure 2B, Table 1) in
638 spent catalysts. The characteristic peaks intensity increased with reduction temperature, probably due
639 to increasing content of γ -Al₂O₃ in fresh catalysts and its transformation into boehmite. Indeed, the
640 acidity of the reaction medium increased with time (feed pH: 8; collected liquid product after 2 h
641 TOS pH: 4, as due to the dissolved CO₂), enhancing the hydration of γ -alumina. Formation of
642 boehmite was also confirmed by FTIR of the spent catalysts (Figure S3B, Supporting Information).
643 For the samples reduced at 700 and 850 °C, NiO was also detected by XRD, which confirmed the re-
644 oxidation of nickel surface, in agreement with TPR results.

645 The amount of exposed Ni area dramatically dropped after APR tests (Table 2). For example, the
646 exposed Ni area for the most active catalyst NiAl-850 decreased from 3.47 m²/g (fresh catalyst) to
647 0.23 m²/g (2 TOS), what represents a 93% decrease. However, the observed leaching and particle
648 migration and sinterization cannot explain such a drop in the exposed area. This observation could be
649 the result of the formation of core-shell particles under APR conditions [75], comprised of metallic
650 Ni core and metal oxide shell. The catalytic activity decay was in line with the amount of re-oxidized
651 Ni as measured from TPR analysis.

652 Regarding the nickel particle growth, it occurred rapidly, as determined by XRD analysis. For
653 example, after two hours of TOS, particle size increased from around 8-14 nm to 42-46 nm (Table
654 1). Thereafter, it did not substantially increase after 50 h of usage (for example, for NiAl-850 catalyst,
655 metallic nickel crystallite size was 44.1 nm). The opposite trend observed for NiAl-700 catalyst
656 suggests leaching of larger particles, what is in direct contradiction with that reported by others where
657 small particles are main source of leached species [74]. Nickel particles of NiAl-600 with the initial
658 smaller particle size outgrow those of samples NiAl-700 and NiAl-850, and all the spent catalysts
659 ended up with similar particle size. This is consistent with theories on particle migration [74] where
660 the initial particle growth rate is larger for smaller particles, and the rates decrease as the average
661 particle size increases. It appeared that the average Ni particle size of spent catalysts was not
662 significantly affected by the activation temperature. However, a subtle decreasing trend could be

663 deduced as reduction temperature increased, what could be ascribed to stronger interaction of Ni
664 particles with the support.

665 Leaching of Ni and Al was also considered given the acidity of the reaction medium (pH decreased
666 to 4 with TOS). The ICP data (Table 1) revealed that leaching of Al from the support was negligible.
667 Leaching of Ni occurred during APR, however, it was minimal even under high glycerol conversion
668 conditions (i.e. about 0.2% Ni leached for NiAl-850 catalyst).

669 Spent catalyst after 50 h TOS contained small amounts of carbonaceous deposits (0.2-1.0 mmolC/g)
670 (Table 1), lesser than typical values reported in the literature (up to 10 mmolC/g) [61,76], which makes
671 the nickel aluminate spinel-derived catalysts resistant to deactivation by coke. Moreover, XRD of spent
672 catalysts (Figure 2B) showed the absence of diffraction peaks of graphitic carbon, reflecting its low
673 content.

674 Based on the characterisation of spent catalysts, it seemed that the main causes of activity decay were
675 nickel re-oxidation and sintering, while metal leaching and coke formation had subtle effect.

676 **3. Conclusions**

677 Stoichiometric bulk nickel aluminate spinel was prepared by coprecipitation and calcination at
678 850 °C. The effect of reduction temperature, between 300 and 850 °C, on physicochemical properties
679 and catalytic performance in the APR of glycerol were investigated.

680 Results clarify that pore volume was hardly affected upon reduction (300-850 °C), with minor
681 alterations in specific area and average pore size. Also, XRD, DRS-UV and FTIR analyses confirmed
682 the good stability of the spinel structure. The used coprecipitation method led to defective Ni-Al
683 mixed oxides, where metallic nickel diffused to the solid surface, strongly interacting with the bulk,
684 what provided very small metallic nickel particles (< 14 nm). It was noticed that hydrogen treatment
685 increased surface density of medium strength acid and basic sites, in detriment of weak and strong
686 sites.

687 It is remarkable the high performance shown by our nickel aluminate catalysts in glycerol APR, in
688 spite of the high space velocity (WHSV 24.5 h⁻¹). The most active assay was that reduced at 850 °C
689 with 93% glycerol conversion, 57% conversion to gas and 62% selectivity to gas (at 250 °C/45 bar).
690 The maximum specific hydrogen production rate was achieved upon reduction at 600 °C, due to
691 adequate ratio between Ni⁰ and accessible support.

692 For all the prepared assays, hydrogen was the main compound in the gaseous stream, followed by
693 carbon dioxide and methane. The low formation of CO suggested that WGS was also favoured by

694 our NiAl₂O₄-derived catalysts to form H₂ and CO₂. Other small chain alkanes were hardly detected
695 what evidenced the high C-C scission ability of the investigated catalysts.

696 Reduction temperature had a more marked effect on the liquid phase product distribution. Results
697 suggested a key contribution of accessible metallic sites and medium strength acidic sites to the
698 overall reaction scheme, with the glycerol reforming occurring through both the dehydrogenation to
699 glyceraldehyde, and through dehydration of terminal hydroxyl groups, and subsequent hydrogenation
700 to yield 1,2-propylene glycol. Activation at 700 °C or above favoured dehydrogenation mechanism,
701 whereas dehydration/hydrogenation mechanism was dominant for catalysts reduced below 600 °C.

702 Long term catalytic runs revealed the good durability of Ni aluminate spinel catalysts, where
703 deactivation occurred mainly through nickel re-oxidation and sinterization, which, indeed, modified
704 the distribution of gas and intermediate liquid products with TOS.

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709 **4. References**

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900 FIGURE ANS SCHEME CAPTIONS

901 Figure 1. H₂-TPR profiles for (A) fresh samples; (B) catalysts used in APR reaction: NiAl-T-u:
902 used for 2 h at 235 °C/35 bar; NiAl-T-50 h: used for 50 h at 235 °C/35 bar.

903 Figure 2. XRD spectra of the fresh samples (A) and spent catalysts (B).

904 Figure 3. DRS UV-vis NIR spectra of the samples, obtained at ambient temperature, and detailed
905 spectra in the 500-800 nm region.

906 Figure 4. Chemical shift (A) and variation of chemical shift of Al_{OH} with reduction temperature (B).

907 Figure 5. Surface acid sites density (A) and Surface basic sites density (B).

908 Figure 6. (A) Glycerol conversion, conversion to gas, hydrogen yield and selectivity to gas. (B)
909 Specific hydrogen production rate. Reaction conditions: 250 °C/45 bar (0.5 g of catalysts,
910 feed rate 0.2 mL/min, 10 wt.% glycerol in water mixture, WHSV= 24.5 h⁻¹, data at steady
911 state = 2 h).

912 Figure 7. Gas phase composition (dry basis) (in bars), and total gas flow (line).

913 Figure 8. (A) Molar composition of the main liquid products, and (B) mole distribution between
914 products of dehydrogenation and dehydration/hydrogenation. Reaction conditions: 250
915 °C/45 bar (0.5 g of catalysts, feed rate 0.2 mL/min, 10 wt.% glycerol in water mixture,
916 WHSV= 24.5 h⁻¹, data at steady state = 2 h).

917 Figure 9. Effect of operation conditions (T/P) on the catalyst performance: (A) gas phase, and (B)
918 liquid phase.

919 Figure 10. Evolution of X_{Gly} (blue), X_{gas} (grey) and S_{gas} (red) with TOS. Filled symbols: NiAl-850;
920 Open symbols: NiAl-700. Reaction conditions: 235 °C/35 bar (0.5 g of catalysts, feed rate
921 0.2 mL/min, 10 wt.% glycerol in water mixture, WHSV= 24.5 h⁻¹).

922 Figure 11. Variation of reaction indices with TOS. (A) NiAl-700; (B) NiAl-800; (C) Liquid phase
923 indices.

924 Scheme 1. Reaction pathway proposed for the glycerol APR on nickel aluminate spinel-derived
925 nickel catalysts.

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Table 1. Textural and structural characteristics of the fresh and spent catalysts.

Sample	Fresh samples							Spent samples						
	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	d _{NiAl₂O₄} ^a (nm)	d _{Ni} ^{0a} (nm)	Phases detected ^a	Acidity ^b μmol _{NH₃} /m ²	Basicity ^c μmol _{CO₂} /m ²	Acid/basic sites ratio	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	d _{Ni} ^{0a} (nm)	d _{boehmite} ^a (nm)	Phases detected ^a	Leached Ni ^d (%)	Leached Al ^d (%)	C ^e (mmol _C /g)
NiAl-c	98.0	8.9	n.d.	NiAl ₂ O ₄	1.57	0.66	2.4	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
NiAl-300	94.9	9.9	n.d.	NiAl ₂ O ₄	1.57	0.59	2.7	102.6	33.9	n.d.	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄	0.65	<0.025	n.a.
NiAl-450	93.5	9.2	n.d.	NiAl ₂ O ₄	1.93	0.39	4.9	87.0	30.0	n.d.	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄	0.78	<0.025	n.a.
NiAl-600	89.8	9.8	7.7	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄	1.82	0.73	2.3	110.2	45.9	8.1	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄ + boehmite	0.72	<0.025	n.a.
NiAl-700	83.1	9.1	13.6	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄	1.70	1.13	1.6	97.4 (92.6)	44.5 (32.0)	15.0 (7.7)	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄ + boehmite	0.27 (6.5)	<0.025 (<0.025)	(1.12)
NiAl-850	76.6	7.0*	11.6	Ni ⁰ + γ-alumina	2.13	1.03	2.0	109.9 (102.9)	41.5 (44.1)	17.4 (7.5)	Ni ⁰ + NiAl ₂ O ₄ + boehmite	0.19 (5.4)	<0.025 (<0.025)	(0.16)

^a from XRD. ^b from NH₃-TPD. ^c from CO₂-TPD. ^d from ICP-AES. ^e carbonaceous deposits by TPO-MS.

* γ-alumina

In parentheses, data for experiments with TOS 50 h

Table 2. Results from H₂-TPR and H₂ chemisorption of the calcined NiAl-c and fresh reduced NiAl-T and used catalysts (2 h TOS).

Sample	Fresh samples								Used samples		
	H ₂ consumption (mmolH ₂ /g)			Distribution of Ni (mmol Ni/g)					H ₂ chemisorption	H ₂ -TPR	H ₂ chemisorption
	TPR-a	TPR-c	f _{Ni,red} (%)	As Ni ⁰	As Surface NiO (peak α)	As Ni _{1-x} Al ₂ O _{4-x} (peak β)	As NiAl ₂ O ₄ (peak γ)	mole ratio β ₁ /β ₂	Ni ⁰ area (m ² /g _{cat})	Oxidised Ni (%)	Ni ⁰ area (m ² /g _{cat})
NiAl-c	5.2	-	-	0 (0.0)	0.08 (1.5)	2.32 (44.7)	2.79 (53.8)	1.10	0	n.a.	n.a.
NiAl-300	-	5.0	3.8	0.20 (3.8)	0.10 (1.9)	2.32 (44.5)	2.59 (49.7)	0.90	0.07	< Q.L.	0.01
NiAl-450	-	4.9	5.8	0.30 (5.9)	n.d	2.19 (42.8)	2.63 (51.4)	0.72	0.10	< Q.L.	0.03
NiAl-600	-	4.1	21.1	1.10 (21.4)	n.d	1.30 (25.3)	2.74 (53.3)	0.47	0.48	124	0.06
NiAl-700	-	2.3	55.8	2.90 (56.2)	n.d	0.30 (5.8)	1.96 (38.0)	0.44	1.63	43 / 34*	0.08
NiAl-850	-	0.01	99.8	5.19 (99.8)	n.d	0 (0)	0.01 (0.2)	0	3.47	45 / 34*	0.23

In parentheses, as mole %

*, values for 50 h TOS

Q.L. Quantification level

Table 3. Comparison of the performance of nickel aluminate spinel-derives catalysts with other researches for APR of glycerol.

T (°C)/ P (bar)	Reactor	Catalyst	Feed, WHSV or gly/cat	X _{Gly} (%)	X _{gas} (%)	S _{H2} (%)	Y _{H2} (%)	S _{gas} (%)	Ref.
250/50	Fixed-bed	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ , CP, 5% Ni	10% gly/w, 2.45 h ⁻¹	67	87	-	-	43	[49]
250/50	Fixed-bed	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ , IMP, 10% Ni	10% gly/w, 2.6 h ⁻¹	40	10	-	-	25	[9]
250/20	Fixed-bed	Ni/LaAlO ₃ , DP, 15% Ni	15% gly/w, 5.2 h ⁻¹	23	-	61	-	-	[50]
240/40	Fixed-bed	Ni/CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ , IMP, 6% Ni, 3% CeO ₂	1% gly/w, 12 h ⁻¹	26	-	49	12	-	[51]
250/35	Fixed-bed	Ni/HTLC, CP, 20% Ni, Al/Al+Mg=0.24	10% gly/w, 5.1 h ⁻¹	30	16	31	10	18	[13]
250/25	Fixed-bed	Ni/Ce _{0.3} Zr _{0.7} O ₂ , CP, 10% Ni	10% gly/w, 2.45 h ⁻¹	90	99	-	-	37	[52]
225/28	Microreactor Fixed-bed	Pt-Re/AC, IMP, 3%Pt, 3%Re	10% gly/w, 5.0 h ⁻¹	88	58	24.5	-	22	[53]
250/45	Batch	Pt-K/HT, IMP, 1%Pt, 2.8%K	10% gly/w gly/cat=0.1, t=4 h	88	87	-	48	33	[54]
225/27.6	Fixed bed	Pt/MgO, IMP, 0.79% Pt	5% gly/w, 3.6 h ⁻¹	-	38	60	28	-	[55]
250/45	Fixed bed	NiAl ₂ O ₄ , CP, 33% Ni	10% gly/w, 24.5 h ⁻¹	93	57	23	21	62	This work

gly/w: glycerol to water weight ratio in the feed, continuous reactor
 gly/cat: glycerol to catalyst weight ratio in the feed, batch reactor
 t: reaction time, batch reactor
 HTLC: hydrotalcite-like compound
 AC: activated carbon

IMP: impregnation
 DP: deposition-precipitation
 CP: coprecipitation

Table 4. Experimental results for the APR of 10 wt% glycerol at 250 °C and 45 bar over NiAl-T catalysts for 2 h

Catalyst	S _{gas} (%)	S _{H₂} (%)	S _{CH₄} (%)	H ₂ /CO ₂	CO/H ₂	Y _{H₂} (%)	S _{C₂} (%)	S _{C₃} (%)
NiAl-300	~0	95	0	4.7	0	0.7	0	0
NiAl-450	~0	90	0	5.6	0	1.4	0	4.95
NiAl-600	31.2	18	17	2.2	0.032	12.3	0.44	0.23
NiAl-700	53.1	21	23	1.6	0.018	18.4	0.47	0.27
NiAl-850	61.9	23	26	1.6	0.015	21.1	0.43	0.23
Ni	39.1	56	0	5.4	0.00	1.58	0	0

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 8

FIGURE 9

FIGURE 10

FIGURE 11

**NICKEL ALUMINATE SPINEL-DERIVED CATALYSTS FOR THE AQUEOUS PHASE
REFORMING OF GLYCEROL: EFFECT OF REDUCTION TEMPERATURE**

A. Morales-Marín¹, J.L. Ayastuy^{1,*}, U. Iriarte-Velasco², M.A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz¹

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

**Corresponding author: jose Luis.ayastuy@ehu.eus*

1. Textural characterization

Figure S1. N₂ physisorption isotherms (A) and pores size distribution (B) for fresh (NiAl-T) and used (NiAl-T-u) samples.

Table S1. Textural properties of the fresh and used (2 h TOS) catalysts.

Sample	Fresh samples		Used samples	
	V _P (cm ³ /g)	d _P (nm)	V _P (cm ³ /g)	d _P (nm)
γ-alumina	0.13	3.6	-	-
NiAl-c	0.27	8.4	-	-
NiAl-300	0.27	8.3	0.27	7.9
NiAl-450	0.28	8.4	0.22	7.7
NiAl-600	0.28	9.1	0.33	9.1
NiAl-700	0.29	10.8	0.33	10.6
NiAl-850	0.29	11.8	0.31	8.3

2. Structural characterization

The unit cell parameters of the nickel-containing phases identified by XRD (NiAl_2O_4 and Ni^0) were also calculated from the XRD diffractograms (Table S3). Spinel crystallized into $Fd-3m$ cubic system (JCPDS 00-010-0339) while metallic nickel crystallized ordinarily into $Fm-3m$ cubic system (JCPDS 01-087-0712). Exposition to hydrogen atmosphere notably decreased the unit cell parameter of the nickel aluminate spinel, more pronounced with the increase of the reduction temperature (from 0.8044 nm for NiAl-c to 0.8010 nm for NiAl-700). According to Halevy et al. [1] this could be explained in terms of the compressive residual stresses generated during reduction of the mixed oxide.

The unit cell parameter of the metallic nickel was almost unaffected (around 0.352 nm) independent of the reduction temperature, which suggested that metallic nickel phase was not transformed, for example, into a quite unusual hexagonal close packed phase [2].

Figure S2. Shift of the peak at 65° with reduction temperature with respect to (440) plane of NiAl-c.

Figure S3A shows the IR skeletal spectra of the fresh NiAl samples. The spectra for NiO and γ -alumina have also been included for comparison purposes. For NiO, a broad band at $400\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the vibration of Ni-O bond was observed revealing the presence of NiO nanocrystals [3]. IR bands related to the physically adsorbed water were almost unappreciable, due to the low water adsorption capacity of NiO as a consequence of its very low surface ($S_{\text{BET}}=0.1\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). For γ -alumina the broad peak at around 3410 cm^{-1} (with three defined peaks at 3415 , 3454 and 3542 cm^{-1})

was due to the presence of surface hydroxyl groups (OH stretching–Al–OH) and peaks at 1619 and 1637 cm^{-1} were due to OH⁻ bending. The absorption bands below 1000 cm^{-1} corresponded to the vibrational modes of coordinated aluminum oxides i.e. bending modes of O–Al–O (484 cm^{-1}) and stretching modes of Al–O–Al (607 cm^{-1}) [4]. Substantial differences were found in the spectrum of NiAl-c sample, in comparison to NiO. Similarly to γ -alumina, the broad band at 3422 cm^{-1} was assigned to the O–H stretching mode of water, while bands at 1382, 1505 and 1638 cm^{-1} were related to the vibration mode of the adsorbed water (not shown) [5].

Figure S3. FTIR spectra of fresh catalysts (A) and spent catalysts (B).

The intense bands at 725 cm^{-1} and 492 cm^{-1} observed for NiAl-c are characteristic of spinel structure [6,7]. The broad bands at about 3420 cm^{-1} can be attributed to hydroxyl stretching and the bands at 1631, 1498 and 1385 cm^{-1} are due to OH bending [6]. The FTIR spectra significantly varied with reduction temperature. For instance, the bands characteristic for spinel remained for catalysts treated at low temperature (NiAl-300 and NiAl-450). Upon treatment above 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ these bands disappeared and characteristic features of γ -alumina could be observed (484 cm^{-1} O–Al–O bending mode, 607 cm^{-1} Al–O–Al stretching mode) and a single OH bending at 1631 cm^{-1} [4]. It could be concluded that NiAl-c mainly contained nickel aluminate phase, which was readily transformed into γ -alumina under H_2 flow at 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

FTIR spectra of catalysts NiAl-700 and NiAl-850 used for 50 h TOS (Figure S3(B)) revealed the existence of boehmite (611, 1068, 3089 cm⁻¹) [8].

Table S2. Structural parameters of the fresh catalysts.

Sample	$a_{\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4}$ ^a (Å)	a_{Ni^0} ^a (Å)	I_{220}/I_{440} ^a	$\text{Ni}^{2+}_{\text{Td}}/\text{Ni}^{2+}_{\text{Oh}}$ ^b	Exposed Ni ⁰ (atNi ⁰ /g _{cat})
NiAl-c	8.044 ± 0.0063	n.d.	0.25	1.44	0
NiAl-300	8.040 ± 0.0060	n.d.	0.25	1.35	1.14 · 10 ¹⁸
NiAl-450	8.036 ± 0.0088	n.d.	0.24	1.31	1.53 · 10 ¹⁸
NiAl-600	8.028 ± 0.0053	3.520 ± 0.0026	0.22	n.d.	7.37 · 10 ¹⁸
NiAl-700	8.010 ± 0.0061	3.519 ± 0.0032	0.21	n.d.	25.1 · 10 ¹⁸
NiAl-850	7.879 ^c	3.522 ± 0.0021	n.d.	n.d.	53.4 · 10 ¹⁸

^a from XRD. ^b from DRS UV-vis NIR.

3. Acidity-basicity

Temperature programmed desorption (Figure S4) was used to characterize the acid and basic strength distribution, assuming that the desorption temperature could be related to the strength of acid and basic sites. In NH_3 -TPD, the peaks observed in the low (below 250 °C), medium (250-500 °C) and high temperature (above 500 °C) regions corresponds to weak, medium and strong acid sites, respectively.

Three temperature intervals were considered in CO_2 -TPD: <150 °C, ascribed to the weak basic sites (decomposition of bicarbonates on surface hydroxyl groups); 150-350 °C, related to the medium strength basic sites (decomposition of bidentate carbonates species); and >350 °C due to the strong basic sites, which are due to the decomposition of the unidentate carbonates species) [9]. Moreover, the unidentate and bidentate carbonates are formed on surface oxygen atoms of different coordination degree (unidentate over oxygen ions showing the lowest coordination number, bidentate over adjacent cationic site [10]).

Figure S4. (A) NH_3 -TPD and (B) CO_2 -TPD profiles for NiAl-T catalysts.

4. Catalytic performance: Effect of working Temperature/Pressure conditions

Figure S5. Alkane selectivity in function of C numbers.

Figure S6. Route A/route B products for different T/P conditions.

Table S3. Gas phase composition, selectivities and hydrogen yield for different T/P operation conditions.

Catalyst	T (°C)/ P (bar)	H ₂ (%)	CH ₄ (%)	S _{gas} (%)	S _{H₂} (%)	S _{CH₄} (%)	H ₂ /CO ₂	CO/H ₂	Y _{H₂} (%)
NiAl-300	235/35	90.0	0.1	0	n.a.	n.a.	n.a	0.00	n.a.
	250/45	82.4	0.1	0	95	0	4.7	0.00	0.7
	260/50	82.4	0.1	6.0	98	0	4.8	0.00	0.9
NiAl-450	235/35	85.0	0.1	0	87	0	5.9	0.00	1.3
	250/45	85.0	0.2	0	90	0	5.6	0.00	1.4
	260/50	78.0	0.1	11.1	93	0	3.9	0.00	1.4
NiAl-600	235/35	54.2	20.4	30.0	19	17	2.5	0.03	10.6
	250/45	52.7	20.3	31.2	18	17	2.2	0.03	12.3
	260/50	51.8	20.2	36.5	20	18	2.1	0.04	14.4
NiAl-700	235/35	52.5	18.4	43.1	23	20	2.1	0.02	15.6
	250/45	46.1	21.4	53.1	21	23	1.6	0.02	18.4
	260/50	45.0	23.5	56.2	20	25	1.6	0.02	18.6
NiAl-850	235/35	48.0	19.7	52.1	22	21	1.6	0.02	16.9
	250/45	45.6	22.5	61.9	23	26	1.6	0.02	21.1
	260/50	43.4	25.0	71.5	23	30	1.5	0.01	22.4
Ni	235/35	73.5	0.1	42.0	93	0	2.8	0.00	2.1
	250/45	84.3	0.2	39.1	56	0	5.4	0.00	1.6
	260/50	90.4	0.1	48.0	50	0	9.4	0.00	1.8

5. H₂-TPR of the spent catalysts

Table S4. TPR data for catalysts used in glycerol APR (2 h TOS at 250 °C/45 bar).

Catalyst	H ₂ consumption (mmol _{H2} /g)			
	Total	Interval 50 - 600 °C	Interval 600 - 750 °C	> 750 °C
NiAl-300	4.46	0.12	1.92	2.42
NiAl-450	4.49	0.03	1.89	2.57
NiAl-600	3.33	1.36	0.43	1.54
NiAl-700	2.41 (1.85)	1.24 (0.99)	0.12 (0.26)	1.05 (0.60)
NiAl-850	2.56 (1.89)	2.34 (1.78)	0.22 (0.11)	n.d. (n.d.)

In parenthesis, data for catalysts used during 50 h (TOS)

6. References Supported Material

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